

From Formative to Embedded: A Conceptual Model for Measuring Information Utilization Maturity in Higher Education

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In today's data-filled society, institutions are abundant with information but lacking in the transformation of information to knowledge and further utilization of knowledge to support actionable change. The focus of the present study was to develop an instrument to gauge institutional maturity with regard to the level in which information is utilized to support decisions, planning, and change. The findings from a field test yielded a conceptual model to assess institutional maturity of information utilization. Additionally, the pilot of the IUMI instrument found high rates of internal reliability and may be used as a catalyst to spark institutional movement towards a culture of evidence-informed practice.

Keywords— Data utilization, higher education, business intelligence, culture of evidence, institutional assessment, research policy, strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

The Information Age and Digital Revolution have created, in essence, a data feedback loop, where volumes of data are generated, tracked, stored, interpreted, expressed, acted upon, and regenerated. This ecosystem of data has implications for both the public and private sectors of the economy, and further, society as a whole. In the purview of this research, the implications of such data availability and usage will be examined, as they specifically relate to institutions of higher education. The following research conceptualizes a method to classify the utilization of information through the lenses of awareness, access, application, and action.

II. SURVEY OF RECENT LITERATURE

The work of Yanoksy and Arroway (2015) led to the determination that analytics continues to be a hot topic throughout higher education; however, institutional maturity regarding data analytics has remained stagnant. As Swing and Ross (2016) stated, "Data don't speak for themselves, and they never talk to strangers." Therefore, one can postulate that higher education institutions are the proverbial strangers in this scenario and that data is not easily interpreted without information literacy. Further, creating a culture of evidence-informed decision-making goes beyond awareness of data systems, but is engrained with policies and practices around accessibility, application, and action with data.

Gagliardi and Wellman (2014) stated, "Institutional leaders need to meet unprecedented public demand for information while also doing more with data to improve performance within their institutions." Wyden and Rubio (2014) also found that many institutions affirm that data is critical to validate best

practices and build stronger programs. The US Department of Education (2017) emphasized that access to data is critical to identify gaps in student performance and to supporting decisions that foster change. This suggests that effective institutional change is a derivative of the utilization of information and thus affirms the need to make information accessible and usable for different constituents. Carmichael's (2015) research supports this notion by indicating that institutional advancement will require that both educators and administrators have access to data to drive measurable performance results. Relatedly, Brown (n.d.) suggests that data should be easily accessible and interpretable to promote user engagement. As colleges collect, store, and report information, it is important to consider the usability of data to support discussion and decision-making. Therefore, in order to move beyond an institution with a plethora of data to an institution with a wealth of knowledge, data must be palatable to support institutional strategy and change.

During an interview, Thirsk stated "Data is growing faster than anybody's technical or intellectual capability to process it or understand it" (Pelletier, 2015). The Lumina Foundation (2017) suggested that building an environment that supports the utilization of data to inform change goes beyond having technical departments (e.g., Institutional Research (IR) and Information Technology (IT)), but requires institution-wide commitment to using data.

Swing and Ross (2016) advocated that students, faculty, and staff are decision makers that each have a unique position in empowering the achievement of institutional missions and that IR has shifted from being the source of information to functioning more as a coach or orchestrator with the use of information. As institutions become further entrenched in data, IR professional will play an essential role in empowering employees to utilize data (Swing and Ross, 2016). It is therefore imperative that IR professionals have access to the necessary data so that they may effectively act as coaches to successfully support decision makers in moving their institution forward. However, Swing, Jones, and Ross (2016) found that while IR departments are considered the central source for institutional data, many departments have only partial or restricted access to institutional information.

While access to data is the starting point for effective information utilization, data must be interpretable and applicable to the respective consumer. Menon, Terkla, and Gibbs (2014) support that a clear understanding and an associated meaningfulness to data is essential when engaging individuals to utilize information that will impact action. Dalhstrom (2016) concludes that institutional culture is a major contributor to fostering the acceptance of data utilization and is

guided by leadership, policies and infrastructure that ensure institutional success. Moreover, implementing strategies for developing information palatability will help fortify the use of data as part of the decision-making process.

III. METHODS

The findings of the survey of recent literature uncovered four common areas related to information utilization in higher education. These areas include:

Awareness: Having a clear understanding of what information is available

Access: Having the ability to obtain information

Application: Understanding how to read, analyze, and use data to support decision-making

Action: Using information to facilitate discussion and make decisions that support planning and change

A field test was conducted with 12 college researchers throughout the U.S. to obtain feedback on the level of importance of the four measures of data utilization (i.e. awareness, access, application, and action). Each participant was asked to rank the categories based on level of importance when seeking to build a culture of evidence-informed decision-making at their institution. The population consisted of executive-level administrators, managers, and technical professionals in the field of higher education research and planning. The findings showed awareness as the highest ranked category, followed by access, application, and action, which is indicative of a linear process of information utilization.

A conceptual model called the information utilization maturity index (IUMI) was developed based on the findings from the field test ranking, with each of the four measures weighted according to the level of importance indicated overall. Figure 1 shows the IUMI model with the applied weights where information utilization maturity is comprised of 35% awareness, 25% access, 20% application, and 20% action.

Figure 1 IUMI Model

A 41-item instrument was developed to assess the four composite measures of information utilization. Table 1 provides

a description of the measures that comprise the instrument, as well as the corresponding Likert scales.

Table 1 IUMI Instrument

Measure	Measure Description	Scale
Awareness	Participants understanding of availability of nine common research-related tools and documents (e.g. surveys, data warehouse, reports).	Not aware of Not available Limited availability Fully available
Access	Participants access to nine common research-related tools and documents (e.g. surveys, data warehouse, reports).	No access Limited access Full access
Application	Participants frequency of use of nine common research-related tools and documents (e.g. surveys, data warehouse, reports)	Do not have access Never Rarely (1-4 Times) Sometimes (5-8 Times) Regularly (9-12 Times) Frequently (13-16 Times) Very Frequently (More than 16 Time)
Action	Participant's use of data before or after making a decision in relation to five different institutional settings. Participant's perception of the college's use of data before or after making a decision in relation to committee and college-wide decisions.	Never Rarely (1%-20%) Sometimes (21%-40%) Nearly half the time (41%-60%) Most of the time (61%-80%) Almost always (More than 80%)

A composite IUMI score for an institution can be calculated based on the weighted model in Figure 1.

Stages of Maturity

The IUMI score is used to determine the level of maturity of information utilization for the institution overall. Institutional maturity is categorized into four stages based on IUMI score quartiles, ranging from formative to embedded. Table 2 provides a description of each stage of maturity.

Table 2 Stages of IUMI

Stage	Description	IUMI Score
Formative	The institution is at the entry level or introductory phase of data utilization	0.0 to 25.0
Pilot	The institution utilizes data sporadically when available	25.1 to 50.0
Advocate	The institution has a general interest in and seeks to utilize data throughout many facets of the college	50.1 to 75.0
Embedded	There is an applied culture of evidence-informed practice that is embedded throughout the college	75.1 to 100.0

Colleges may consider adding supplemental questions to the IUMI assessment to include college occupational demographic information (e.g., employee job classification, tenure status, and department) as means to identify gaps in information maturity between sub-populations of the institution.

Validation

A pilot study was conducted to assess the reliability of the composite measures that make up the information utilization maturity index. The survey was distributed electronically to a collection of 713 full-time faculty, part-time faculty, classified staff, and administrators. The survey yielded a 14.7% response rate with 105 valid responses. Each measure was analyzed to determine reliability, in addition to the index overall. Table 3 indicates that the four measures and the overall instrument have high internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha > 0.9).

Table 3 *Reliability Testing*

Measure	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Awareness	9	0.936
Access	9	0.940
Application	9	0.954
Action	14	0.959
IUMI (overall model)	41	0.976

IV. IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

As the breadth of information continues to expand, it is recommended that institutions continually strengthen their knowledge, skills, and abilities to mine, analyze, and more importantly, utilize data to support action. The IUMI model provides an opportunity for institutions to assess their level of data utilization and further provides a starting point to support policy change and professional learning. While the instrument has been piloted and shows potential for scalability in supporting institutional change, future research is recommended to determine effective strategies for engaging college constituents (i.e. faculty, staff, and administration) with information for use in institutional and departmental planning.

V. DISCUSSION

In today's data-filled society, institutions are abundant with information but lacking in the transformation of information to knowledge and further utilization of knowledge to support actionable change. The focus of the present study was to develop an instrument to gauge institutional maturity with regard to the level in which information is utilized to support decisions, planning, and change. The findings from the field test yielded a conceptual model to assess institutional maturity of information utilization. Additionally, the pilot of the IUMI instrument found high rates of reliability and may be used as a catalyst to spark institutional movement towards a culture of evidence-informed practice.

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